

Bank Muamalat Indonesia: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Bank Muamalat Indonesia using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Muamalat Indonesia " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Muamalat Indonesia based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 7 mapping research topics using literature studies about Bank Muamalat Indonesia, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; (6) Accounting treatment; and (7) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Muamalat Indonesia, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Muamalat Indonesia; Library Research

Introduction

The development of Indonesian society who adhere to Islam is increasing. The large number of Muslim people in Indonesia has an impact on various fields, one of which is the increasing development of sharia banking. Sharia banks are commercial banks which in all their activities and operations apply sharia principles. And also, services and products are developed based on provisions in the Al - Qur'an and hadith (Wilardjo, 2019). Bank Muamalat Indonesia (BMI) was the first sharia bank to be established and was the pioneer of the establishment of other sharia banks.

Bank Muamalat Indonesia (BMI) is the first sharia bank established in Indonesia. Bank Muamalat Indonesia actually existed around 1970, but only in 1991. This was due to political factors which believed that the establishment of a sharia bank was a result of the ideals of establishing the Islamic caliphate (Uswatun Khasanah, 2020). Quoted from the official website of Bank Muamalat Indonesia, based on Deed of Establishment No. 01 which was made on March 21 1992 in front of Yudo Paripurno, SH, Notary, in Jakarta, Bank Muamalat was established on November 1 1991. Bank Muamalat Indonesia was founded based on the initiative of the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI), the Indonesian Muslim Scholars Association (ICMI), and also from Muslim entrepreneurs who receive support from the Indonesian government.

Bank Muamalat Indonesia has a high level of fame and is known by many people. This is because Bank Muamalat Indonesia was the first sharia bank established. Many scientific articles use Bank Muamalat Indonesia as an object of research. There are 725 scientific articles on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) which research Bank Muamalat Indonesia from 1996 to 2022.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Muamalat Indonesia using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Muamalat Indonesia, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank Muamalat Indonesia, both frequently and rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Bank Muamalat Indonesia (BMI) is the first Islamic bank in Indonesia to apply sharia principles in all its operations. Bank Muamalat Indonesia is a public company whose company shares are not listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange (BEI). On October 27 1994, this bank officially operated as a Foreign Exchange Bank on the basis of the Bank Indonesia board of directors' decision letter No. 27/76/KEP/DIR (Bankmuamalat, 2016).

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Methodology

This research uses a qualitative approach in the nature of a library research. The object of the research is Bank Muamalat Indonesia. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles about Bank Muamalat Indonesia. The source of data collection came from searching the accredited national journal Sinta via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and Perish/Harzing software. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then searching for journals based on the title words category with the key word " Bank Muamalat Indonesia " within the entire year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Muamalat Indonesia based on the journals that have been collected.

Results and Discussion

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of Bank Muamalat Indonesia

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 33 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Muamalat Indonesia, namely:

1. First, disclosure of Islamic values and earnings management in financial reports.
2. Second, the effect of bad loans and capital adequacy ratio on return on equity.
3. Third, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Operational Costs on Operational Income/BOPO, Loan to Deposit Ratio/LDR, Murabahah financing, Mudharabah financing, Ijarah financing, Mudharabah savings, Mudharabah financing income, Non Performing Financing/NPF, long-term debt, problem financing, currency exchange rates, operational efficiency, macroeconomics, composition of non-profit sharing financing, working capital turnover, Net Interest Margin/NIM, Musyarakah contracted working capital financing, Fee Based Income, Profit Sharing Based Income, Covid-19, Non-Performing Loans/NPL, and inflation on profitability/Return On Assets/ROA/Return On Equity/ROE.
4. Fourth, the influence of Mudharabah financing, Murabahah financing, Musyarakah financing, foreign exchange income, promotional costs and operational income on the company's net profit.
5. Fifth, the influence of profitability ratios, solvency ratios, liquidity ratios, profitability ratios, Economic Value Added/EVA, sukuk issuance, profit and loss, added value, Islamicity Performance Index, Bank Indonesia Regulations/PBI, corporate zakat, Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR, Funds Third Party/DPK, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Balanced Scorecard, Branchless Banking, and Income Statement Approach to measuring financial performance.
6. Sixth, measuring the level of bank health using the Risk Profile, CAMEL, company fundamentals through financing, IPI and RGEC (Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, Capital) methods.
7. Seventh, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Return On Assets/ROA, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Gross Domestic Product/GDP, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, inflation, provision of Murabahah financing, and currency exchange rates on Non-Performance Financing/NPF.
8. Eighth, measuring the bank's growth level using the balanced scorecard method.
9. Ninth, the influence of Debt Financing, Equity Financing on Profit Expense Ratio.
10. Tenth, measuring company performance/quality using the Islamic Performance Index method.
11. Eleventh, measurement of Operational Costs against Operational Income/BOPO, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Non-Performing Financing/NPF, Return on Assets/ROA, Cash Ratio, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Allowance for Losses of Productive Assets/PPAP.
12. Twelfth, measuring company efficiency uses the Data Envelopment Analysis/DEA method and financial ratios.
13. Thirteenth, the influence of Cash Ratio and Murabahah financing on Murabahah margin income.

14. Fourteenth, the influence of Mudharabah financing, Musyarakah financing, Ijarah financing on profitability.
15. Fifteenth, the influence of advertising and personal selling costs on deposit sales.
16. Sixteenth, the influence of the quality of financing and the quality of Human Resources/HR on revenue effectiveness.
17. Seventeenth, the influence of inflation and exchange rates on ujarah in Musyarakah Mutanaqisah financing.
18. Eighteenth, the influence of deposit interest rates, deposit profit sharing, rupiah exchange rate against the US dollar, Jakarta Islamic Index/JII, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, and Return On Equity/ROE on the price of sharia bonds/sukuk.
19. Nineteenth, the influence of Murabahah financing, problematic financing, cash turnover, short-term debt, and Covid-19 on liquidity.
20. Twentieth, the influence of inflation, per capita income, SWBI rewards on the amount of Hajj bailout funds.
21. Twenty-first, the influence of Third Party Funds/DPK on economic profitability.
22. Twenty-second, internal control system for the cash receipts function.
23. Twenty-third, the influence of systematic risk and liquidity on stock returns.
24. Twenty-fourth, predicting financial distress uses the bankometer model approach, Altman and Grover.
25. Twenty-fifth, the influence of promotional costs, marketing strategies for savings products, and the implementation of the forecast hybrid package on Third Party Funds/DPK.
26. Twenty-sixth, the influence of Return On Assets/ROA, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Operational Expenses on Operating Income/BOPO on financial distress.
27. Twenty-seventh, the influence of Return On Assets/ROA, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Net Interest Margin/NIM, BI rate on Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR.
28. Twenty-eighth, the effect of Musyarakah financing on asset growth.
29. Twenty-ninth, the influence of profit sharing financing and buying and selling on the company's net margin.
30. Thirtieth, the influence of Covid-19 on Non Performing Financing/NPF and Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR.
31. Thirty-one, the influence of profit sharing income, Murabahah margin income, and wadiah savings funds on wadiah bonuses.
32. Thirty-second, the influence of liquidity, GAP management and foreign exchange management in Assets and Liability Management/ALMA on Net Profit Margin/NPM.
33. Thirty-third, the influence of equity and Third Party Funds/TPF on profit growth.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Muamalat Indonesia Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 57 topics related to the performance of Bank Muamalat Indonesia employees, namely:

1. Trustworthy.
2. Organizational culture.

3. Celestial incentives.
4. Company image.
5. Discipline.
6. Social support.
7. Economic incentives.
8. Islamic work ethics.
9. Paternalistic leadership style.
10. Social security health.
11. Front office employees.
12. Permanent and contract employees.
13. Job characteristics.
14. Organizational characteristics.
15. Professional commitment.
16. Organizational commitment.
17. Internal auditor performance.
18. Management performance.
19. Compensation.
20. Sharia/Islamic competency.
21. Intellectual and spiritual intelligence.
22. Knowledge management.
23. Teamwork.
24. Work ability.
25. Work engagement.
26. Suitability of study major.
27. Interpersonal communication.
28. Emotional stability.
29. Educational background.
30. marketing.
31. Human Resource Management.
32. Work motivation.
33. Religious motivation.
34. Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation.
35. Avoid usury.
36. Islamic values.
37. Individual values.
38. Organizational development.
39. Career development.
40. Understanding sharia values.
41. Workforce leveling.
42. Employee placement.
43. Training.
44. Psychological empowerment.
45. Punishment.
46. Rewards.
47. Recruitment.
48. Religiosity.
49. Selection.
50. Reward system.
51. Spirituality.
52. Spiritual leadership.
53. Payroll accounting information system.
54. Spatial.

55. Maslow's hierarchical theory of methods.
56. Efficiency level.
57. Wage match level.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Muamalat Indonesia Customer Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 79 topics related to Bank Muamalat Indonesia customer behavior, namely:

1. Automatic Teller Machine/ATM.
2. Contract.
3. Services marketing mix.
4. Share savings and financing profits.
5. Brand associations.
6. Brand switching.
7. BI rate.
8. Company image.
9. Corporate image.
10. Covid-19.
11. Customer service.
12. Demographics.
13. Discipline.
14. Differentiation.
15. Digital Islamic Network.
16. Digital Fintech.
17. Brand equity.
18. E-Banking.
19. Islamic ethics.
20. Emotional.
21. E-Muamalat.
22. Facility.
23. Financial attitude.
24. Financial technology.
25. Geography.
26. Advertisement.
27. Internet banking (perception of usefulness, ease of use, risk).
28. Culture.
29. Utility.
30. Convenience.
31. Comfort.
32. Personality.
33. Trust.
34. Satisfaction.
35. Commitment.
36. Integrated marketing communications.
37. Service quality.
38. Service quality.
39. Utility.
40. Confidence.
41. Profit.
42. Sharia compliance.
43. Environment.

44. Financial literacy.
45. Location.
46. Marketing mix.
47. Mobile banking.
48. Motivation.
49. Customer value.
50. Parking.
51. Service.
52. Education.
53. Behavior.
54. Complaint handling.
55. Handling problems.
56. Islamic marketing.
57. Understanding.
58. Front liner service.
59. Private sales.
60. Price perception.
61. Knowledge of purchasing and usage.
62. Positioning.
63. Funding products.
64. Savings products.
65. Performance.
66. Sales promotion.
67. Privacy risk.
68. Psychological.
69. Publicity.
70. Education payments.
71. Income.
72. Religiosity.
73. Relationship marketing.
74. Financing risk.
75. Rational.
76. Brand reputation.
77. Social.
78. Time risk.
79. Word of mouth.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Muamalat Indonesia Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 37 research topics related to Bank Muamalat Indonesia financing products, namely:

1. First, the influence of savings, own capital, Non-Performing Loans/NPL, Third Party Funds/DPK, level/percentage of profit sharing, profit markup, deposits, total assets, Return On Assets/ROA, Non-Performing Financing/NPF on financing.
2. Second, the application of Murabahah fines according to the DSN-MUI fatwa as a non-halal funding scheme.
3. Third, financing analysis using the information mining method.
4. Fourth, supervision of business capital financing for purchasing goods.

5. Fifth, judicial resolution of problematic financing/bad credit and the impact of force majeure on natural disasters, and its impact on reducing the level of Non-Performing Financing/NPF.
6. Sixth, Mudharabah financing risk management with a linkage program strategy, executing pattern.
7. Seventh, determining the Murabahah financing margin.
8. Eighth, the application and procedures for financing Sharia Home Ownership Credit/KPR using Murabahah, Musyarakah Mutanaqisah, Ijarah Muntahiya Bit Tamlik/IMBT contracts according to PSAK 106.
9. Ninth, implementation of Mudharabah and Musyarakah financing according to Fatwa No. 84/DSN-MUI/XII/2012.
10. Tenth, financing the profit sharing system according to Law no. 21 of 2008.
11. Eleventh, guarantee/financing collateral.
12. Twelfth, the KPRS financing take-over process is based on the principle of notarial prudence.
13. Thirteenth, marketing criminal responsibility for problematic financing.
14. Fourteenth, the influence of Third Party Funds/DPK, BI 7 Day (Reverse) repo rate, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, profit margin, Bank Indonesia Wadiah Certificate/SWBI, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Return On Assets/ROA, Non Performing Financing/NPF, inflation, number of branches, and Shariah Compliance with Murabahah financing.
15. Fifteenth, implementation of micro business financing according to sharia law.
16. Sixteenth, the influence of Third Party Funds/DPK, Mudharabah savings, Mudharabah Deposits, and problematic financing on Mudharabah financing.
17. Seventeenth, the influence of Murabahah margins, conventional bank mortgage interest, and ujarah on the growth rate of Sharia Home Ownership Credit/KPR joint financing.
18. Eighteenth, the bank's treatment of financing claims for the destruction of collateral.
19. Nineteenth, application of value added tax on Murabahah financing products.
20. Twentieth, Murabahah financing for employee and multipurpose cooperatives.
21. Twenty-first, the influence of the BI rate, profit sharing financing of Mudharabah, Musyarakah, and the level of profit sharing towards Mudharabah profit sharing income.
22. Twenty-second, the role of women as financing policy makers.
23. Twenty-third, a profit sharing scheme as a solution to the principal-agent problem in Mudharabah financing.
24. Twenty-fourth, branch collection communication patterns in the process of collecting problematic financing from debtors.
25. Twenty-fifth, Murabahah financing disputes from the perspective of sharia economic law.
26. Twenty-sixth, application of audit based risk on Murabahah receivables.
27. Twenty-seventh, the performance of internal auditors in preventing fictitious credit fraud.
28. Twenty-eighth, Ijarah Multijasa financing for re-planting oil palm plantations.

29. Twenty-ninth, application of the 5C principles in financing distribution.
30. Thirtieth, auction of collateral.
31. Thirty-one, financing restructuring.
32. Thirty-second, criminal liability for fictitious working capital financing.
33. Thirty-third, Maqashid Syariah achievements in financing.
34. Thirty-fourth, implementation of Mudharabah financing (PSAK 105) and Qardhul Hasan.
35. Thirty-fifth, the influence of customer income on the rate of return on Murabahah financing.
36. Thirty-sixth, settlement of customer defaults on Home Ownership Credit/KPR.
37. Thirty-seventh, application of the Qardh agreement to financing the Hajj bailout.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Muamalat Indonesia Savings Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 16 research topics related to Bank Muamalat Indonesia savings/savings products, namely:

1. First, designing a savings service information system.
2. Second, the influence of financial performance, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Return On Assets/ROA, Operational Costs on Operating Income/BOPO, and inflation on the profit sharing rate of Mudharabah savings.
3. Third, the influence of profit sharing levels, interest rates, liquidity and inflation on the amount of Mudharabah savings/deposits.
4. Fourth, procedures for collecting savings data.
5. Fifth, calculation of profit sharing received by customers.
6. Sixth, the application of the Mudharabah Muthlaqah agreement to savings products.
7. Seventh, sharia financing model for the agricultural sector.
8. Eighth, the influence of savings on the community's economy.
9. Ninth, determining the amount of profit sharing ratio on deposit products.
10. Tenth, the influence of conventional bank interest rates and inflation on savings volume.
11. Eleventh, savings program with prize plans, Hajj and Umrah savings (with the Wadi'ah Yad Dhamanah agreement) with SWOT analysis.
12. Twelfth, implementation of fatwa no. 03/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 and positive law regarding Mudharabah deposits.
13. Thirteenth, a savings product with a Mudharabah Muthlaqah agreement, in the form of iB Hijrah Prima.
14. Fourteenth, the influence of the work ethic of the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS on the supervision of deposit products and Rahn.
15. Fifteenth, the influence of wadi'ah demand deposits, wadi'ah savings and time deposits on profit growth.
16. Sixteenth, review of Islamic law regarding giving gifts/bonuses in wadi'ah savings agreements.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Accounting Treatment at Bank Muamalat Indonesia

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 7 research topics related to accounting treatment at Bank Muamalat Indonesia, namely:

1. First, measuring company performance/quality using the financial accounting information quality method.
2. Second, measuring financing transactions using the profit sharing principle in accounting concepts.
3. Third, application of accounting information systems in internal control of Musyarakah financing.
4. Fourth, gharar in recording accounting accruals.
5. Fifth, Mudharabah sharia accounting according to financial accounting standards.
6. Sixth, accounting treatment of Musyarakah Mutanaqisah contracts, Istishna' contracts, Musyarakah financing, and Mudharabah profit sharing income.
7. Seventh, the internal control system in financing procedures uses an accounting information system.
8. (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Emiliani et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Zahro et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rahmawati et al., 2023) (Shalsabila et al., 2023) (Fitriawati et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Febrian & Budianto, 2023) (Rohmah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) .

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues at Bank Muamalat Indonesia

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 36 research topics related to issues at Bank Muamalat Indonesia, namely:

1. First, the birth process of Bank Muamalat Indonesia as a sharia economic reform.
2. Second, customer behavior and satisfaction using the logistic regression analysis method.
3. Third, bank guarantee products and cash waqf Law no. 41 of 2004.
4. Fourth, the existence of Bank Muamalat Indonesia.
5. Fifth, social responsibility (CSR) uses a humanist approach, an emancipatory approach, and Sharia Enterprise Theory/SET.
6. Sixth, the principle of profit sharing with the concept of net revenue sharing in Mudharabah transactions.
7. Seventh, the application of wadiah contracts, Murabahah bil Wakalah (working capital financing), Musyarakah, and Kafalah.
8. Eighth, implementation of economic democracy.
9. Ninth, comparison of profit and interest sharing systems.
10. Tenth, analyze potential bankruptcy using the Altman method.
11. Eleventh, the influence of the promotion model on market share.
12. Twelfth, mitigating the risk of money laundering crimes.

13. Thirteenth, calculation of zakat funds according to the Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions/AAOIFI.
14. Fourteenth, implementation of Good Corporate Governance/GCG from an Islamic sharia perspective.
15. Fifteenth, application of maqashid sharia in Corporate Social Responsibility/CSR.
16. Sixteenth, formulate the company's business strategy using the Boston Consulting Group/BCG matrix and the Tows-K matrix.
17. Seventeenth, the influence of bank products (Murabahah, Musyarakah, Mudharabah financing) on the growth of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises/MSMEs.
18. Eighteenth, the influence of consulting and the balanced scorecard on management performance results.
19. Nineteenth, vulnerability to the global economic crisis.
20. Twentieth, measuring company performance uses the Maqashid Syariah Index, efficiency level, Islamic Corporate Governance, and Islamicity Performance Index.
21. Twenty-first, the impact of the convergence of International Financial Reporting Standards/IFRS.
22. Twenty-second, productivity of zakat management from the profit sharing system.
23. Twenty-third, disclosure of Islamic Social Reporting/ISR.
24. Twenty-fourth, application of the principle of customer due diligence in order to prevent money laundering crimes.
25. Twenty-fifth, implementation of sharia compliance as a principle of sharia governance in Sharia Financial Institutions.
26. Twenty-sixth, implementation of a whistleblowing system against internal fraud.
27. Twenty-seventh, implementation of PSAK No. 101 to the profitability ratio.
28. Twenty-eighth, credit risk management.
29. Twenty-ninth, the influence of Covid-19 on operational risk.
30. Thirtieth, legal protection for confidential customer data from an Islamic banking legal perspective.
31. Thirty-one, the influence of financial performance and the implementation of Good Corporate Governance/GCG on potential bankruptcy.
32. Thirty-second, profit analysis, company size, Return On Assets/ROA on zakat payments.
33. Thirty-third, the implementation of sharia compliance in the Wakalah bil Ujrah contracted pension program.
34. Thirty-fourth, elimination of the Hajj bailout agreement.
35. Thirty-fifth, implementation of cash waqf.
36. Thirty-sixth, implementation of green banking.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 7 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Muamalat Indonesia, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; (6) Accounting treatment; and (7) Other issues.

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